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SELECTIVE AND SENSITIVE RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF TACROLIMUS IN CAPSULE DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Tacrolimus is used as an immunosuppressant. The method developed is used for assay tacrolimus in pharmaceutical dosage form. A simple, rapid and reproducible high performance reverse phase liquid chromatographic method has been developed for quantitative estimation of Tacrolimus in tablets form using a, Phenomenex 250 mm x 4.9 mm C18, 5 μm, inertsil and UV detection at 220nm. The isocratic elution was used to quantify the analyte and the mobile phase was Acetonitrile: water (50: 50) was pumped at 1.0 ml/min. The method was linear between 50-300 μg/ml, statistically validated for its linearity, precision and accuracy. The intra-and - inter day variation was found to be less than 1% showing high precision of the assay method. The method selective and sensitive which is used for the estimation of tacrolimus in presence of excipients in the commercial capsules did not interfere with the method.

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INTRODUCTION

Its IUPAC name: (1R, 9S, 12S, 13R, 14S, 17R, 18E, 21S, 23S, 24R, 25S, 27R) -1, 14- dihydroxy- 12- [(1E) - 1 - [(1R, 3R, 4R) - 4 - hydroxyl - 3 - methoxycyclohexyl] prop - 1 - en - 2 - yl] - 23, 25 - dimethoxy - 13, 19, 21, 27 - tetramethyl - 17 - (prop - 2 - en - 1 - yl) - 11, 28 - dioxo - 4 azatricyclo [22.3.1.0.] octacos-18-ene-2,3,10,16-tetrone.(3).

The mechanism of action of tacrolimus during clinical significance of these observations in atopic dermatitis is not known. Here tacrolimus is first binding to an intracellular protein, FKBP-12 and it inhibits T- Lymphocyte activation. The phosphatase activity of calcineurin is inhibited by a complex of tacrolimus-FKBP-12, calcium, calmodulin, and calcineurin. This prevents the dephosphorylation and translocation of nuclear factor of activated T-cells (NF-AT), a nuclear component thought to initiate gene transcription for the formation of lymphokines. Tacrolimus also inhibits the transcription for genes which encode IL-3, IL-4, IL-5, GM-CSF, and TNF-, all of which are involved in the early stages of T-cell activation. Additionally, tacrolimus has been shown to inhibit the release of pre-formed mediators from skin mast cells and basophils, and to downregulate the expression of FcεRI on Langerhans cells. (2), (3) several methods have been described for determination of Tacrolimus in pharmaceutical preparations including HPTLC, HPLC and NMR had been used for the determination of Tacrolimus. The proposed method is selective and sensitive for assay of tacrolimus in pharmaceutical dosage form with sensitivity of LOQ 0.318µg/ml. (4), (5), (6), (7).

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials:

All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade and purchased from Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India. Acetonitrile HPLC grade, Water HPLC grade, ortho phosphoric acid, Tacrolimus Standard.

Preparation of solutions:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Make a mobile phase in the ratio of Acetonitrile: water (50:50) adjusts the pH at 4.0 with diluted phosphoric acid. Filtered through 0.45 micron membrane filter.

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Standard Solution: 150ppm of Tacrolimus (Prepared standard in duplicate for similarity)

Accurately weigh and transfer 50 mg of Tacrolimus standard into a 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 3ml acetonitrile and sonicate to dissolve and dilute up to mark with same medium and mix it well.

Dilute 1.5 ml of this solution to 10 ml with ACN solution.

Selection of wavelength for analysis of Tacrolimus:

Accurately weigh and transfer 50 mg of Tacrolimus standard into a 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 3ml acetonitrile and sonicate to dissolve and dilute up to mark with same medium and mix it well.

Dilute 1.5 ml of this solution to 10 ml with ACN solution.

The resulting solution was scanned in UV range (200nm–400nm). In spectrum Tacrolimus showed absorbance maximum at 220 nm.

Validation of the method:

The method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, and ruggedness.

Linearity study:

Different aliquots of Tacrolimus in range 50 - 300 µg/ml were transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and the volume was made up to the mark with acetonitrile to get concentrations, respectively.

Table 1: Linearity of Tacrolimus.

Tacrolimus peak			
Conc. µg/ml	Avg. Area (n=6)	SD	%RSD
50	614994	2.50	0.0004%
100	1239988	2.51	0.0002%
150	1848982	2.17	0.0001%
200	2469976	1.52	0.00006%
300	3659964	2.17	0.00005%
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Figure 1: Linearity Plot.

Figure 2: HPLC Chromatograph of Tacrolimus.

Table: 2: Overlay linearity for Tacrolimus.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Tacrolimus
1	Linearity range	50 - 300µg/ml
2	Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9999
3	Intercept	0
4	Slope	12267
5	Precision	
	Intraday Average % RSD (n = 5)	0.163
	Inter day Average % RSD (n = 5)	1.26
6	Reproducibility of measurements %RSD	0.059
7	% Recovery	99.51-100.66
8	Limit of detection (µg/ml)	0.0905
9	Limit of quantification (µg/ml)	0.318

Accuracy:

To the preanalysed sample solutions, a known amount of standard stock solution was added at different levels i.e. 80%, 100% and 120%. The solutions were reanalyzed by proposed method.

Precision:

Precision of the method was studied as intra-day and inter-day variations. Method Intra-day precision was determined by analyzing the 150ppm solution of Tacrolimus for method precision and system precision have been. Inter-day precision was determined by analyzing the 150 ppm solution of Tacrolimus daily for three days over the period of week.

Sensitivity:

The sensitivity of measurements of Tacrolimus by the use of the proposed method was estimated in terms of the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) and Limit of Detection (LOD). The LOQ and LOD were calculated using equation $LOD = 3.3 \times N/B$ and $LOQ = 10 \times N/B$, where, 'N' is standard deviation of the peak areas of the drugs (n = 3), taken as a measure of noise, and 'B' is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

Repeatability:

Repeatability was determined by analyzing 150 ppm concentration of Tacrolimus solution for six times.

Ruggedness:

Ruggedness of the proposed method is determined for 0.1 mg/ml concentration of Tacrolimus by analysis of aliquots from homogenous slot by two analysts using same operational and environmental conditions.

Determination of Tacrolimus in bulk:**Test solution: 150 ppm of Tacrolimus:**

Take 20 capsules Find out the average weight and take the powder equivalent to 50 mg of Tacrolimus, are introduced into a 50ml volumetric flask. Approx. 20 ml of acetonitrile was added and shaken well. The solution is sonicated for approx. 15 minutes.

Following cooling to room temperature, the solution is filled up to volume with acetonitrile, mixed well and then filtered through a 0.45µm nylon membrane. The first 5 ml of filtrate are discarded. 1.5ml of this solution are diluted to 10.0ml with acetonitrile and mixed well.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Method Validation:**

The proposed method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The solutions of the drugs were prepared as per the earlier adopted procedure given in the experiment.

Linearity studies:

The linear regression data for the calibration curves showed good linear relationship over the concentration range 50-300 µg/ml for Tacrolimus. Linear regression equation was found to be $y = 12180x + 18000$, $R^2 = 0.999$

Accuracy:

The solutions were reanalyzed by proposed method; results of recovery studies are reported in Table 2 which showed that the % amount found was between 98.54% to 99.98% with %R.S.D. >2.

Precision:

The precision of the developed method was expressed in terms of % relative standard deviation (% RSD). These result shows reproducibility of the assay. The % R.S.D. values found to be less than 2, so that indicate this method precise for the determination of both the drugs in formulation.

Sensitivity:

The linearity equation was found to be $Y = 12180x + 18000$. The LOQ and LOD for Tacrolimus were found to be 0.038 μg and 0.32 μg , respectively.

Repeatability:

Repeatability was determined by analyzing 150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentrations of Tacrolimus solution for six times and the % amount found was between 98% to 102% with % R.S.D. less than 2.

Ruggedness:

Peak area was measured for same concentration solutions, six times. The results are in the acceptable range for both the drugs. The results are given in Table 5. The result showed that the % R.S.D. was less than 2%

Determination of Tacrolimus in bulk:

The concentrations of the drug were calculated from linear regression equations. The % amount found was between 99.17% to 100.43%.

Application of proposed method for pharmaceutical formulation:

The spectrum was recorded at 281 nm. The concentrations of the drug were calculated from linear regression equation. The % amount was found between 98.36% to 101.31%.

CONCLUSION

The HPLC method has been developed for quantification of Tacrolimus capsule formulation. The validation procedure confirms that this is an appropriate method for their quantification in the API and formulation. It is also used in routine quality control of the raw materials as well as formulations containing this entire compound as per study the future research proposed in impurity and tacrolimus analysis in same method.

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Abbreviations:-

ICH	: International Conference on Harmonisation
TCL	: Tacrolimus
API	: Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients
UV	: Ultra Violet
CAN	: Acetonitrile
HPLC	: High performance Liquid Chromatography
HPTLC	: High performance Thin Layer Chromatography
NMR	: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

Originality:-

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